

NeoGiANT - The power of grape extracts: antimicrobial and antioxidant properties to prevent the use of antibiotics in farmed animals

Project Number: 101036768

STORABLE Cluster Kick-off meeting

2025-10-09 from 9:00 to 13:20 (CET)

Venue: on-line, Google Meet link:

<https://meet.google.com/wgd-nsit-zam>

Attendants:

- NeoGiANT WP6 partners (invitation to NeoGiANT's coordinators)
- Bullnet MSCA DN
- AFRODITA MSCA DN
- CryoStore MSCA DN
- ANDRO-EXPERT iLink DN
- CONEREPRO UCM research group
- Semen Cardona SL (LE)
- Topigs Norsvin Research Center B.V. (LE)
- AIM Ibérica (LE)
- Precisión Celular (SME)

LE: large enterprise

Agenda (CET time):

Topic	Responsible	Time
Welcome and STORABLE's purpose	Felipe Martínez-Pastor (Bianor) and Úrsula Álvarez (Magapor) (STORABLE coordinators)	9:00–9:10
Welcome from NeoGiANT's coordinators and NeoGiANT's purpose	Marta Lores (NeoGiANT's coordinator)	9:10–9:20
NeoGiANT reproduction WPs presentation (purpose and achievements)	Felipe Martínez-Pastor (NeoGiANT's WP6 coordinator) Semen extender formulation using natural extracts	9:20–9:40

Q&A on STORABLE and NeoGiANT	All participants	9:40–10:00
Bullnet presentation	Sean Fair	10:00–10:10
ANDRO-EXPERT presentation	Manuel Álvarez-Rodríguez	10:10–10:20
CryoStore presentation	Ian Mayer	10:20–10:30
Q&A on DN	All participants	10:30–10:50
Break		10:50–11:10
CONERPRO presentation	Alejandro Vicente-Carrillo	11:10–11:20
Semen Cardona presentation	Xavier Barrera	11:20–11:30
Topigs Norsvin RC presentation	Rodrigo Mezencio	11:30–11:50
AIM Ibérica presentation	M. José Martínez-Alborcia	11:50–12:00
Precisión Celular presentation	Sofía Manso	12:00–12:10
Q&A on enterprises and research groups	All participants	12:10–12:30
Break		12:30–12:50
Round-up and discussion on next webinar planning	STORABLE coordinators/all participants	12:50–13:15
Closing of the kick-off meeting	Felipe Martínez-Pastor and Úrsula Álvarez	13:15–13:20

After the meeting:

Post-webinar survey:

<https://cryptpad.fr/form/#/2/form/view/K+NrZkG3bonnESLzcvAISbcRWie9MtHMrM94SRiwpN8/>

Form for requesting an attendance certificate:

<https://cryptpad.fr/form/#/2/form/view/sy7FW9NJTpbA6HFSjDcAV0Zr52IMU6lgtiA1Pv138cE/>